

DIDACTICAL PRINCIPLES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDIA LITERACY AND INFORMATION CULTURE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article describes the didactic principles of developing media literacy and information culture of students. Information is also provided that the use of media education in the educational process teaches students to think independently, develop their worldview, intellectual potential, creative activity, receive information, process it, generalize, and draw the necessary conclusions. It is worth noting that today it is appropriate to carefully study the theoretical foundations of media education and apply them in practice. The process of globalization places special demands on the education system. These requirements are directly and indirectly related to the introduction of media education into the educational process.*

Keywords: *student, teacher, education, media literacy, information culture, media education, knowledge, tool, principle.*

Introduction. It should be emphasized that the system of higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, capable of forming such important personal qualities as "devotion to the ideals of national independence, loyalty to national traditions, humanism and high spirituality" [2], is called upon to solve the most important tasks of forming these strategies. Therefore, the issue of developing media literacy and information culture of students of higher educational institutions in the process of mastering the content of academic disciplines of media education, capable of "fostering high spirituality and morality, patriotism and a sense of pride in their homeland, their people, their historical past" [1], is of particular relevance.

The use of media tools in organizing classes allows to bring training to a higher substantive and qualitative level, to increase the level of media literacy, information culture and to use them effectively in the educational process. In the educational process, the teacher, along with providing students with theoretical knowledge, has the opportunity to clearly demonstrate educational materials using modern innovative technical means and achieves high efficiency of the educational process [6].

- **Literature review.** It is important to highlight that Kh. Dostmukhammad, M. Mirsoatov, A. Nurmatov and others conducted research on the use of media tools in the educational process, the formation of media literacy and information culture in the context of the development of modern communication technologies.

- **Research methodology.** Nowadays, education in our republic has changed dramatically, that is, other content, other approaches, other attitudes, other behavior, a different level of pedagogical processes, a different pedagogical mentality are recommended, including [8]:

- the content of education is enriched with new, more advanced skills and competencies, actions with information, development of abilities, creative solutions to scientific problems and practice based on innovative technological equipment in educational programs;

- traditional methods of transmitting information - oral and written speech - are giving way to computer teaching aids, the use of an extensive telecommunications network;

- an important organizer of the pedagogical process is communication between a teacher and students, focused on the individual;

- special importance is attached to the spiritual education of the individual, the moral character of a person;

- The role of science in the creation of modern information, pedagogical, innovative, interactive and non-traditional teaching technologies is growing.

- **Analysis and results.** The word "media" comes from the Latin word "media", which means "means", "intermediary", or more precisely, "mass media". The term "media education" was first defined in 1973 by the International Film and Television Council: "Media education consists of teaching the theory of mass media (mass media) and developing skills in working with them."

UNESCO defines media education as "the study of the theory and practice of knowledge of modern mass media" [9]. Currently, in countries such as European countries, the USA, Australia and Russia, media education is included in the education system as a compulsory subject.

It is of particular significance that effective results can be achieved by organizing the educational process using modern methods and technologies, pedagogical technologies and didactic teaching aids, using didactic principles as their basis. Currently, all didactic principles have been analyzed and revised in accordance with the needs of society and the achievements of pedagogy. Let's get acquainted with the content of these didactic principles [4].

The principle of awareness and activity is to ensure active and conscious participation of students in the educational process. To implement this principle in practice, it is necessary to adhere to the following principles [3]:

- disclose the content of new materials and their connection with other subjects;

- determine the level of assimilation of each new topic by students with the help of questions;

- ask questions at a level corresponding to the thinking and needs of each student;

- demonstration of practical application of theoretical knowledge;

- implementation of independent thinking of students, etc.

The principle of clarity. The most effective among human systems in obtaining, effectively using and memorizing external information is the visual system. When applying the principle of clarity, it is necessary to adhere to the following:

- attracting the attention of all students to clarity when explaining new material;

- use of virtual information technologies in the lesson;

- development of imagination and abstraction of students through the use of visual aids;

- involvement of students in the preparation of certain visual aids, the formation of practical skills and abilities in working with them, etc.

The principle of systematization and consistency. The topics of each subject studied should be taught in a certain system, in accordance with their features. Consistency between new material and previously presented material should be ensured.

The implementation of this principle requires:

- preliminary planning of the material studied, dividing it into logically related parts, determining the order of work with each of them and the methodology for its assimilation;

- identifying connections between facts, laws and theories in teaching a subject, explaining them in a certain sequence;
- using a practically proven method for forming theoretical knowledge and substantiating the basis for control;
- striving to show the prospects of educational work, etc. [5].

The principle of consistency. The knowledge acquired by students should, firstly, be perceived deeply, and secondly, be remembered for a long time. The implementation of the principle of consistency requires that the student know the material not mechanically, but deeply and accurately.

It merits attention that to implement the principle of consistency, it is necessary to take into account the following:

- do not allow the memorization of additional and secondary materials;
- acquaint students with various teaching aids and additional literature, teach them to work with them;
- teach students to independently repeat the educational material and find answers to unconventional questions;
- develop in students the skills and abilities of independent learning.

The principle of reliability. The educational material should be adequate for the student and the group and presented in a form corresponding to the level of their perception.

For implementing the principle of reliability in the educational process, it is advisable to:

- take into account the life experience of students, the development of their consciousness, interests and level of understanding when teaching each topic;
- prevent stagnation in the growth of the level of knowledge of strong students and create conditions for the growth of those lagging behind;
- widely use research methods of explaining educational material, including observation, analogy, experiment, etc.;
- competently organize students' activities to deepen their knowledge, etc. [7].

The principle of scientific character. The learning process requires the provision of scientific, experimentally confirmed information related to each subject. Therefore, it is advisable to use methods close to and corresponding to the methods of scientific research in teaching students.

It is important to ensure the scientific character of teaching; it is necessary to:

- approach the assimilation of each phenomenon and pattern from a didactic point of view, pay serious attention to the formation of a scientific worldview in students;
- take measures to develop students' interest in research work;
- provide complete information on the latest scientific achievements, as well as on innovative technologies, etc.

The principle of connection between theory and practice. The effectiveness of the learning process and its quality are tested in practice. The result of the educational process depends on the connection between theory and practice, the content of the educational process and the organization of educational work, as well as the interactive methods used.

When applying the principle of connection between theory and practice, the following must be taken into account:

- clearly demonstrate that the content of the disciplines taught in universities is a requirement of life, confirmed by historical and social practice;

- teach the practical application of theoretical knowledge;
- to correctly form students' attitudes to work and production, effectively enhance professional orientation, etc.

The principle of historicity requires the presentation of materials related to the history of science, the struggle of contradictions and ideas in its development, the emergence of scientific achievements, and the contribution of scientists to the development of various scientific fields.

The principle of systematicity. Systematicity is the interconnection of phenomena in the process of development. This is a special manifestation of the laws of dialectics, which concern the transition from negation to negation, quantitative changes to qualitative ones. The main meaning of this principle is that everything new arises on the basis of the old, and in accordance with changes in society, the old retains its strength, and the old is completely refuted. Consequently, systematicity is the main condition for dialectical change and development.

The principle of humanism. Humanism is a view of equality, truthfulness of people and mutual respect between them. The application of the principle of humanity and humaneness in the educational process requires a humane attitude towards each student, considering him as a subject with his own personal views and interests, as well as as an object of education.

Conclusion. Recommendations. In conclusion, it should be noted that if information on the development of media literacy and information culture of students is presented using didactic principles, it will be easier for students to perceive the content of the educational material, the skills of understanding the essence of concepts, laws and arguments presented in the educational material will be formed, the level of their knowledge will increase, their intellectual potential will grow and their worldview will expand.

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